

Kinetic Studies on the Oxidation of Organic Compounds: Part I. Oxidation of Formic Acid by Manganic Sulphate

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Oxidation of formic acid by manganic sulphate has been studied in 4M sulphuric acid. The reaction is of first order with respect to both the reactants. A number of salts have been found to retard the reaction. The rate determining steps are the electron transfer processes. A free radical mechanism has been suggested which is quite in conformity with the observations.

In spite of the huge amount of work done on the oxidation of organic compounds by potassium permanganate the mechanism of the process is still not clear in most of the cases.

In acidic medium, permanganate oxidation involves five electron transitions¹ whereas in alkaline medium it is a three electron transfer process. But little is known about the intermediate steps. Mn(III) is however usually considered to be involved in the rate determining steps. Hence it was considered to be worthwhile to study the mechanism of oxidation of organic compounds by Mn(III).

Drummond and Waters (*loc. cit.*) have reported that the cherryred colour of manganic sulphate is stable in the presence of formic acid. Easy oxidation of formic acid by cerium (IV)² which is as strong an oxidant as manganese (III) sulphate, inspired us to investigate the oxidation of formic acid by manganic sulphate. We have, however, observed that though the colour of manganic sulphate lasts in dilute solution of formic acid, it fades slowly with the evolution of carbon dioxide in fairly strong solution of formic acid.

This communication deals with our results on the oxidation of formic acid by manganic sulphate in acidic medium.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Manganic sulphate: It was prepared by Ubbelohde method³ and stored in a coloured bottle, at about 4°. The solution was standardized before use by titrating it against standard ferrous ammonium sulphate solution.

Kinetic Measurements: Flasks containing solutions of formic acid and manganic sulphate in sulphuric acid were placed in a thermostat. The two solutions were mixed

1. A. Y. Drummonds and W. A. Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 435.
2. N. N. Sharma, *Z. anal. Chem.* 1957, 154-340, (in English).
3. A. R. J. P. Ubbelohde, *ibid*, 1935, 1605.

after they had attained the temperature of the bath. To determine the concentration of Mn(III) in the reaction mixture, 5 ml. aliquot was withdrawn at definite intervals and run into ice-cold water to chill the reaction and titrated against ferrous ammonium sulphate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the presence of large excess of formic acid, the rate of disappearance of manganic ion was found accurately to be of the first order and the rate-constants were calculated

Fig. no. 1

FIG. 1.

First order plot between $\log \text{Mn(III)}$ vs. time.

$\text{Mn(III)} = .02\text{M}$; $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 4.5\text{M}$; $T_{\text{temp}} = 40^\circ\text{C}$

Formic acid, A=1.99M B=2.10M, C=2.36M, D=2.77M

from the slope of the lines obtained by plotting $\log (\text{Mn}^{3+})$ against time (vide Fig. 1). The results are as follows:

TABLE I

$\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 4.5\text{M}$;	$\text{Mn}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 = 0.02\text{M}$;	Temp. 40°C .			
HCOOH (M)	2.31	2.10	1.99	1.59	
$k \times 10^4$	12.92	10.86	9.79	8.65	7.38
(min^{-1})					
$\frac{k \times 10^4}{(\text{HCOOH})}$	4.66	4.70	4.66	4.40	4.64

Besides the above observations the kinetics was followed with a number of intermediary concentrations of formic acid and the reaction was first order throughout. $K/(\text{HCOOH})$ is a constant which indicates a first order dependence on formic acid as well.

The temperature dependence of the reaction has also been investigated. However, as the rate constant is of the complex form $(k_1 + k_2/\text{H}^+)$ no specific information can be had from $\log k \text{ vs } 1/T$ plot.

TABLE II

Concentration of $Mn_2(SO_4)_3$	= 0.022M				
Concentration of HCOOH	= 1.5M				
Concentration of H_2SO_4	= 4.8M				
Temperature ($^{\circ}C$)	41	46	51	56	61
$K \times 10^4 (\text{min}^{-1})$	7.14	11.50	12.70	17.4	20.20

The first order dependence of the rate on either reactants can easily be explained as follows:

As the rate determining step is a bimolecular process between an ion and a neutral molecule, this reaction will have no salt effect. The negative salt effect recorded below (Table III) suggests some slow reaction between ions of opposite sign.

TABLE III

Concentration of Mn^{+++}	= 0.02M							
Concentration of H_2SO_4	= 4.4M							
Concentration of HCOOH	= 2.56M							
Temp. 40°								
			Salt					
	Nil	KCl	KNO ₃		K ₂ SO ₄			
			0.167M	0.66M	0.2M	0.76M	0.07M	0.14M
$K \times 10^4 (\text{min}^{-1})$	14.42	8.33	5.39	8.09	6.71	13.93	11.80	

The negative salt effect of potassium chloride and potassium nitrate is almost same—but it is observed that potassium sulphate has comparatively small salt effect which is perhaps due to suppression of second dissociation of sulphuric acid—i.e., $HSO_4^- \rightleftharpoons H^+ + SO_4^{2-}$. On one hand, the rate is depressed by adding potassium sulphate because one of the slow steps of the reaction involves the interaction of oppositely charged ions—but it is partly compensated by SO_4^{2-} —ions as suppression of second dissociation of sulphuric acid decreases the acid content of the reaction mixture. Nitrates and chlorides do not act as base.

We are, however, of the opinion that increase in rate with manganous sulphate as reported below is due to the existence of the following equilibrium⁴:

Ionic strength of the medium was compensated by adding requisite amount of $ZnSO_4$.

TABLE IV

Concentration of $Mn_2(SO_4)_3$	= 0.015M				
Concentration of HCOOH	= 1.5M				
Concentration of H_2SO_4	= 4.2M				
$ZnSO_4$	Nil	0.04M	0.078M	0.12M	Temp. $40^{\circ}C$.
$MnSO_4$	0.16M	0.12M	0.082M	0.04M	Nil
$K \times 10^4 (\text{min}^{-1})$	22.9	13.7	9.27	7.19	6.92

Bawn and White⁵ have studied the oxidation of formic acid by CO(III), in 8N-sulphuric acid, have given evidence for the existence of the equilibrium, $\text{HCOOH} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}^+ + \text{HCOO}^-$. The negative salt effect suggests a slow reaction between formate ion and Mn^{3+} .

Mn^{3+} would also react with formyl radical as follows:

In the oxidation of formic acid by hydrogen peroxide Weiss⁶ has suggested the following equilibrium between formyl radical and formic acid.

The whole sequence of reaction will therefore be:

Electron transfer analogous (I) and (III) have also been proposed by Bawn and White⁷ in the oxidation of formic acid by cobalt (III) sulphate. Assuming steady state for the free radical HCOO and OH , we arrive at:

$$\frac{d(\text{Mn}^{3+})}{dt} = k_1 (\text{HCOOH}) + k_2 (\text{HCOO}^-) \text{Mn}^{3+}$$

If the reaction No. 2 is slow to disturb the equilibrium, one can substitute for the concentration of formate ion in terms of its equilibrium constant

$$\frac{d(\text{Mn}^{3+})}{dt} = (k_1 + \frac{k_2 K}{\text{H}^+}) (\text{HCOOH}) \text{Mn}^{3+}$$

where K is the dissociation constant for the acid. Since k_1 , k_2 and k are small and H^+ is very large, $k_2 K / \text{H}^+$ can be neglected in comparison to k_1 . The rate-expression thus takes the form:

$$\frac{d(\text{Mn}^{3+})}{dt} = K \text{HCOOH} \text{Mn}^{3+}$$

Thanks are due to Prof. A. R. Kidwai, Head of the Chemistry Department for providing facilities.

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Received, September, 28, 1966

5. C. E. H. Bawn and A. G. White, *ibid*, 1951, 339.

6. Weiss, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1937, 41, 1107.

7. C. E. H. Bawn and A. G. White, *ibid*, 1951, 331.